

RESEARCH OF DATA MINING METHODS

Zaman Zeynalov,*PhD., Azerbaijan State Agricultural University (ASAU),
information Technologies Department.***Ayten Aliyeva,***Ass., Azerbaijan State Agricultural University (ASAU),
information Technologies Department***Naila Hasanova,***Ass., Azerbaijan State Agricultural University (ASAU),
information Technologies Department***Shahla Babayeva,***Ass., Azerbaijan State Agricultural University (ASAU),
information Technologies Department***Aysel Xocayeva***Ass., Azerbaijan State Agricultural University (ASAU),
information Technologies Department***Abstract**

The article discusses data mining methods based on various research materials. Some basic methods and examples of using tools used for data mining are discussed.

Keywords: analysis, methods, data, clustering, decision tree.

Introduction.

Today, the proliferation of communication tools, simplification of their use and lower prices have led to easier access to information [1]. Against the background of the growth of information and communication technologies and improving their quality, the volume of digital information is increasing in geometric rows every year. The expansion of Internet access creates a revival in the growth of the volume of information created and collected at a really huge pace.

The expansion of the Internet and easy access to information are considered various means of distortion and analysis of information.

One such tool is data analysis methods.

Material and method.

Data analysis - the field of mathematics and computer science, engaged in the construction and study of the most common mathematical methods and computational algorithms for obtaining knowledge from experimental (in the broad sense) data; is a process of data research, filtering, transformation and modeling in order to obtain useful information and make decisions [5].

The data analysis process is divided into the following steps [6,7,8,9]:

- Identification of the problem to be solved;
- Data collection;
- Data cleaning;
- Data analysis;
- Creation of a model corresponding to the problem;
- Visualization.

Data analysis is carried out in two directions:

- qualitative analysis through interviews and observations;
- quantitative analysis - by means of surveys and experiments.

There are various methods for analyzing data. These methods can be organized as follows:

Mathematical and statistical methods: descriptive analysis, analysis of variance, regression analysis, factor analysis, discriminant analysis, time analysis;

Methods based on artificial intelligence and machine learning: artificial neural networks, decision trees (decision trees), evolutionary programming, fuzzy logic;

Visualization and graphical representation methods. Bar Chart, Bar Chart, Line Chart, Area Chart, Pie Chart, Funnel Chart, Word Cloud Chart, Word Cloud Chart, Radar Chart, Scattering Chart, Bubble Chart, Gauge, etc.

Of the methods mentioned, recent ones are data mining, which is used in a wider range.

Intelligent data analysis is becoming an increasingly relevant area of research every year in all areas of human activity: banking, insurance, government and others.

Intelligent data analysis (through or data mining) is the process of detecting in "raw" data previously unknown, insignificant, practically useful and interpreted knowledge (patterns) necessary for decision-making in various areas of human activity. This definition is considered classic, but according to the researchers, it consists of several errors:

For example, IBM SPSS ®, based on statistical analysis and surveys, allows you to build effective predictive models of past trends and make accurate forecasts. IBM InfoSphere ® Warehouse provides search, initial processing, and data source intelligence in a single package to extract information from the source database directly into the final report.

Recently, it has become possible to cluster (large-scale) data processing to work with very large data sets, which allows you to summarize the data mining results

by groups and their comparisons in an even more complex form. New tools and systems are available today, including storage and processing [5].

You can analyze various datasets, including traditional SQL databases, raw text data, key/value sets (stack), and documented databases. Clustered databases such as Hadoop, Cassandra, CouchDB, and Couchbase Server provide and support manual data access in ways that do not match the traditional table structure.

In particular, more flexible storage of the document base gives a new direction in the processing of information and complicates it. SQL databases tightly regulate the structure and strictly follow the scheme, which simplifies their queries and data analysis.

Documented databases that follow a standard structure such as JSON, or files with some machine-readable structure, are also easily processed, although work can be complicated by a diverse and variable structure. For example, in Hadoop, which processes completely "raw" data, it can be difficult to detect and extract data before processing and comparison.

The basic methods used for data mining describe the type of data mining and its recovery operation. Unfortunately, different companies and solutions don't always use the same terms, which can add to the confusion and perceived complexity.

Research of intelligent data analysis tools.

Let's look at some basic techniques and examples of using certain data mining tools [8,9,10].

Association (or relation) is probably the most well-known, familiar, and simple mining method. To define models, a simple comparison of two or more elements, often of the same type, is made. For example, by tracking their shopping habits, they can be seen also buying cream along with strawberries.

It is easy to create association or relationship-based mining tools. For example, InfoSphere Warehouse has a wizard that provides information flow configurations for creating associations.

Classification (classification) can be used to get an idea of the type of buyers, goods or objects by describing several attributes to identify a certain class. For example, cars are easy to classify (sedan, SUV, convertible), defining different attributes (number of seats, body shape, driving wheels). Having studied a new car, it can be attributed to a certain class. The same principles can be applied to recipients, such as classifying them by age and social group.

In addition, classification can be used as input to other methods. For example, you can use decision trees to define a classification. Clustering allows common attributes of different classifications to be used to detect clusters.

Clustering. By learning one or more attributes or classes, you can group individual data elements together. At a simple level, clustering uses one or more attributes as the basis for defining a cluster of similar results. Clustering is useful for identifying different data because it is related to other patterns so that you can see how similarities and ranges are consistent with each other.

Forecasting is a broad topic that ranges from predicting the bankruptcy of hardware components to detecting fraud and even predicting the company's profits. Joint data prediction with other mining methods involves trend analysis, classification, model comparison, and relationships. By analyzing past events or copies, you can predict the future.

Sequential models often used to analyze long-term data - a useful method of identifying or regularly repeating trends in such events. For example, it can be determined from information about buyers that they buy certain sets of goods at different times of the year. Based on this information, the customer's cart prediction application can automatically assume that certain items will be added to the cart based on the frequency and date of purchase [9,10].

Decision trees. The decision tree associated with most other methods (mainly classification and prediction) can be used to support the selection of specific data either within the selection criteria or within the overall structure. The decision tree begins with a simple question that has two answers (sometimes more). Each answer leads to the next question, helping to classify and identify data or make predictions.

Decision trees are often used with property classification information systems and prediction systems, where different predictions can be based on past historical experience that helped build the structure of the decision tree and produce results.

Combinations. In practice, only one of these methods is very rarely used. Classification and clustering are such methods. The classification can be further refined by clustering to determine nearest neighbors. Decision trees are often used to construct and define classifications that can be traced back to historical periods to define sequences and models [10].

Memory processing. With all basic methods, it often makes sense to record the information received and study it later. For some methods, that's pretty obvious. For example, sequential modeling and training analyze historical data from various data sources and samples for prediction purposes.

In other cases, this process may be more obvious. Solution trees are rarely installed once and are never forgotten. As new data, events, and data points are identified, additional branches or even completely new trees may need to be installed [10].

Some of these processes can be automated. For example, building a predictive model to detect credit card fraud results in determining the probabilities that can be used for the current transaction and then updating that model when new (validated) transactions are added. This information is then recorded so that a decision can be made more quickly next time.

References

1. <https://ict.az/az/news/914/>
2. <https://banco.az/az/news/data-science-ve-data-scientist-nedir>
3. www.researchgate.net "Verilnrlin-Intelligence-Analysis"

4. https://ict.az/uploads/konfrans/biq_data/1-1_Mkruf_Hacrhimova_-_Big_data_konsep-siyas_v_aktual_elmi-nzri_problemlr.pdf
5. Abbasov A.M., Gasymov V.A., Guliyev R.A. Methods of decision-making in intellectual information systems. Textbook. Baku. 2003,256 p.
6. <http://people.cs.pitt.edu/~пыль/231/y11/paper/chooseDataMining.pdf>
7. Michael Berthold, Christian Borgelt, Data Mining/Intelligent Data Analysis, Paris Lodron University of Salzburg. <https://borgelt.net/slides/ida.pdf>
8. Korneev V.V., Garev A.F., Vasyutin S.V., Reich V.V. Databases: intelligent information processing. M.: Nolidge, 2000, 352 p.
9. <https://www.softwaretestinghelp.com/data-analysis-tools/>
10. Data mining technology: method. decree. In the course "Data Mining Technology" for students of all forms of training in the direction of 230400.62 "Information Systems and Technologies "/comp. V.E. Pospelov; Tyumen State Oil and Gas University. - Tyumen: Publishing Center BIK Tyumen State University 2013. - 20 s.